

Frequent and reliable engraftment of certain adult primary acute lymphoblastic leukemias in mice

Birgitta Christine Heckl^{1*}, Michela Carlet^{1*}, Binje Vick^{1,2}, Catrin Roof³, Ameerah Alsadeq⁴, Michaela Grunert¹, Wen-Hsin Liu¹, Andrea Liebl¹, Wolfgang Hiddemann^{2,5}, Rolf Marschalek⁶, Denis Martin Schewe⁴, Karsten Spiekermann^{2,5}, Christian Junghanss³, Irmela Jeremias^{1,2,7#}

1 Research Unit Apoptosis in Hematopoietic Stem Cells (AHS), Helmholtz Center Munich, German Research Center for Environmental Health, Munich, Germany;

2 German Cancer Consortium (DKTK), partner site Munich, Germany;

3 Department of Medicine III – Hematology, Oncology and Palliative Care, Rostock University Medical Center, Germany;

4 Pediatric Hematology/Oncology, ALL-BFM Study Group, Christian Albrechts University Kiel and University Hospital Schleswig-Holstein, Campus Kiel, Germany

5 Department of Medicine III, University Hospital, LMU Munich, Germany;

6 Institute of pharmaceutical biology, Goethe University, Frankfurt, Germany

7 Department of Pediatrics, Dr. von Hauner Children's Hospital, Ludwig Maximilians University (LMU), Munich, Germany;

correspondence

Irmela Jeremias
Helmholtz Center Munich
Marchioninistraße 25
81377 Munich, Germany
Irmela.Jeremias@helmholtz-muenchen.de
tel. +49 89 3187 1424
fax +49 89 3187 4225

* both authors contributed equally

Word count: 1372

Acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) represents a severe malignant disease of the hematopoietic system and novel treatment options are urgently needed, especially in adults, at relapse and in refractory disease [1, 2]. Preclinical research on ALL is hampered by the fact that primary ALL cells from patients do not reliably grow *in vitro*, while established ALL cell lines often present additional alterations which are rare in patients [3]. In the individualized xenograft mouse model, primary ALL cells of different genetic backgrounds infinitely grow in severely immuno-compromised mice. The mouse model enables convenient work on surrogate patient-derived xenograft (PDX) ALL cells, including studies on leukemia stem cells and leukemia-stroma interaction [4]. While numerous pediatric PDX ALL models exist worldwide [5, 6, 7], engraftment of adult ALL cells appeared challenging so far [8]. Here, we show that primary adult ALL cells of two discrete high-risk cytogenetic groups reliably engraft in mice at high frequencies.

Primary leukemia cells were obtained from 15 adult ALL patients and transplanted into NSG mice (NOD/scid IL2 receptor gamma chain knockout mice; clinical data of patients in Table S1). All samples carried either the chromosomal translocation t(9;22) BCR/ABL (n=10) or t(4;11) MLL/AF4 (n=5) as both are ~~of high prevalence and~~ associated with dismal prognosis in adult patients with ALL requiring better treatment options [9]. Samples were consecutively collected without selection except for the genetic translocation. Samples were mostly transplanted directly at the day of diagnosis without prior freezing/thawing; if unfeasible, cells were frozen and thawed under research conditions using optimized protocols [10]. Cells were transplanted into untreated animals in the absence of preconditioning by, e.g., chemotherapy or irradiation.

High and reliable engraftment was observed for primary adult ALL cells on NSG mice (Figures 1A, 1B, S1A and S1B) and similarly in samples derived from peripheral blood or bone marrow aspiration (Table S2). 9/15 samples induced deadly leukemia in mice within 100

days (Figure 1A) which was associated with an infiltration of the bone marrow by human blasts of above 80 %. Similar to pediatric ALL, adult ALL samples induced splenomegaly in mice, mostly of major extent enabling isolation of up to billions of PDX ALL cells per mouse (data not shown). Within 22 weeks and at the end of the observation period, 13/15 samples showed engraftment of at least 70% human cells in bone marrow (Figure 1B), 8 out of 10 t(9;22) and 5 out of 5 t(4;11) samples. 5/5 (100%) of the directly transplanted and 8/10 (80%) of frozen/thawed samples engrafted (Figure S1A, Table S3), suggesting a putative loss of engraftment capacity due to freezing/thawing.

Our results are in contrast to published data describing low engraftment rates for primary adult t(9;22) BCR/ABL ALL samples unlike pediatric ALL samples, unless mice are pretreated by total body irradiation inducing unspecific inflammation in the bone marrow [8, 11]. As we used similar ALL subtypes and identical mice as one study [8, 11], underlying reasons remain elusive. In general, high quality sample retrieval represents a huge advantage for research accompanying clinical trials. We received primary samples within hours of diagnosis avoiding, e.g., overnight shipping required in certain multicenter trials. Pretreatment of mice by irradiation or chemotherapy might compensate for putative reduced cell viability, but other explanations are also conceivable.

In addition, frozen/thawed cells showed a tendency towards extended periods of time for cell passaging, defined as time from injection of ALL cells to deadly leukemia in mice (82.6 days in fresh versus 102.2 days frozen/thawed samples, in directly versus frozen/thawed samples). Over passaging, the time required for each passage slightly decreased in all samples, remaining constant thereafter. Two samples with slow growth in the first passage showed marked reduction in passaging time down to average levels within the first two passages (Figure 1C).

Taken together, engraftment rates of primary adult ALL samples in mice were very high in our hands and similar to those described for primary pediatric ALL samples [6, 12].

PDX mouse models represent highly valuable tools for preclinical treatment trials and basic studies on disease biology [4, 7]. Genetic engineering facilitates these studies as, e.g., bioluminescence *in vivo* imaging allows accurate follow up of disease development and treatment effects (Figure S2 and S3) [13, 14]. For convenient wording, we propose referring to genetically engineered PDX models as ‘GEPDX’ models in parallel to genetically engineered mouse models (GEMM) [13, 14, 15]. While numerous GEPDX models exist for pediatric ALL, we aimed at establishing GEPDX models from adult ALL samples.

In general, ALL cells are difficult to transduce and require lentiviral transduction which is facilitated by favorable cell viability *in vitro*. Unfortunately, some PDX ALL samples with MLL translocations exhibited limited viability of below 20% living cells after 5 days of culture which was inferior to PDX AML samples with MLL translocation and further aggravated upon freezing/thawing (Figure 1D and S4). Using our established protocols and constructs for expressing transgenes [13, 14], adult PDX ALL cells with BCR/ABL or MLL rearrangement displayed very poor susceptibility towards lentiviruses with mean transduction efficiencies of around 5 % (Figure 1E). In adult PDX leukemia cells with MLL rearrangement, ALL were markedly less prone towards lentiviral transduction than AML cells (5 versus 50% transduction efficiencies, respectively). Pediatric PDX ALL cells with MLL rearrangement showed similar minor transduction rates as adult cells which is in sharp contrast to the favorable transduction efficiency of above 30% in pediatric PDX ALL samples without MLL rearrangement (Figure 1F and S5). However, no correlation was detected between cell viability and transduction efficiency. PDX AML samples used in this study were representative established samples of the lab with representative transduction rates.

Nevertheless and despite these challenges, all adult PDX ALL cells allowed lentiviral transduction and enabled establishing GEPDX models, especially as enrichment of transgenic

cells was performed by flow cytometry using a fluorochrome as molecular marker [13, 14]. As lentivirally transduced samples allowed re-transplantation with similar growth kinetic, transgenic samples had retained stemness and *in vivo* growth behavior.

In summary, our data indicate that primary adult ALL samples engraft at similar rates in NSG mice as pediatric ALL samples. Although adult ALL cells with BCR-ABL or MLL-translocations reveal low survival *in vitro* and low lentiviral transduction rates, genetic engineering is feasible in PDX cells of all types of ALL enabling molecular studies. GEPDX models of acute leukemia might enable a better understanding of disease biology as well as precise preclinical treatment trials which will allow preclinical development of more effective therapies for the benefit of patients with acute leukemia in the future.

The authors thank Annette Frank, Maike Fritschle, Fabian Klein, Miriam Krekel and Liliana Mura for technical support and Michael Hagemann and his team for excellent animal care. The work was supported by ERC Consolidator Grant 681524; Deutsche Jose' Carreras Leukämie-Stiftung (R 10/26), the German Consortium for Translational Cancer Research (DKTK), Bettina Bräu-Stiftung; and Dr. Helmut Legerlotz Stiftung (all to I.J.) and the Collaborative Research Center 1243 Genetic and Epigenetic Evolution of Hematopoetic Neoplasms, project A05 (to I.J.) and A07 (to K.S.); and the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation (to M.C.).

Correspondence: Irmela Jeremias, Helmholtz Zentrum München, Marchioninistraße 25, 81337 München, Germany; e-mail Irmela.Jeremias@helmholtz-muenchen.de.

1. Pui CH, Robison LL, Look AT. Acute lymphoblastic leukaemia. *Lancet* (London, England). 2008 Mar 22;371(9617):1030-43. doi: 10.1016/s0140-6736(08)60457-2. PubMed PMID: 18358930; eng.
2. Bassan R, Hoelzer D. Modern therapy of acute lymphoblastic leukemia. *Journal of clinical oncology : official journal of the American Society of Clinical Oncology*. 2011 Feb 10;29(5):532-43. doi: 10.1200/jco.2010.30.1382. PubMed PMID: 21220592; eng.
3. Petitjean A, Mathe E, Kato S, et al. Impact of mutant p53 functional properties on TP53 mutation patterns and tumor phenotype: lessons from recent developments in the IARC TP53 database. *Human mutation*. 2007 Jun;28(6):622-9. doi: 10.1002/humu.20495. PubMed PMID: 17311302; eng.
4. Ebinger S, Ozdemir EZ, Ziegenhain C, et al. Characterization of Rare, Dormant, and Therapy-Resistant Cells in Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia. *Cancer cell*. 2016 Dec 12;30(6):849-862. doi: 10.1016/j.ccell.2016.11.002. PubMed PMID: 27916615; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC45156313. eng.
5. Townsend EC, Murakami MA, Christodoulou A, et al. The Public Repository of Xenografts Enables Discovery and Randomized Phase II-like Trials in Mice. *Cancer cell*. 2016 Jul 11;30(1):183. doi: 10.1016/j.ccell.2016.06.008. PubMed PMID: 27479034; eng.
6. Woiterski J, Ebinger M, Witte KE, et al. Engraftment of low numbers of pediatric acute lymphoid and myeloid leukemias into NOD/SCID/IL2Rgamma null mice reflects individual leukemogenicity and highly correlates with clinical outcome. *International journal of cancer*. 2013 Oct 01;133(7):1547-56. doi: 10.1002/ijc.28170. PubMed PMID: 23526331; eng.
7. Jones L, Richmond J, Evans K, et al. Bioluminescence Imaging Enhances Analysis of Drug Responses in a Patient-Derived Xenograft Model of Pediatric ALL. *Clinical cancer research : an official journal of the American Association for Cancer Research*. 2017 Jul 15;23(14):3744-3755. doi: 10.1158/1078-0432.ccr-16-2392. PubMed PMID: 28119366; eng.
8. Patel B, Dey A, Castleton AZ, et al. Mouse xenograft modeling of human adult acute lymphoblastic leukemia provides mechanistic insights into adult LIC biology. *Blood*. 2014 Jul 03;124(1):96-105. doi: 10.1182/blood-2014-01-549352. PubMed PMID: 24825861; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC4125358. eng.
9. Gleissner B, Gokbuget N, Bartram CR, et al. Leading prognostic relevance of the BCR-ABL translocation in adult acute B-lineage lymphoblastic leukemia: a prospective study of the German Multicenter Trial Group and confirmed polymerase chain reaction analysis. *Blood*. 2002 Mar 01;99(5):1536-43. PubMed PMID: 11861265; eng.

10. Bonnet D. In vivo evaluation of leukemic stem cells through the xenotransplantation model. *Current protocols in stem cell biology*. 2008 Dec;Chapter 3:Unit 3.2. doi: 10.1002/9780470151808.sc0302s7. PubMed PMID: 19085977; eng.
11. Notta F, Mullighan CG, Wang JC, et al. Evolution of human BCR-ABL1 lymphoblastic leukaemia-initiating cells. *Nature*. 2011 Jan 20;469(7330):362-7. doi: 10.1038/nature09733. PubMed PMID: 21248843; eng.
12. Morisot S, Wayne AS, Bohana-Kashtan O, et al. High frequencies of leukemia stem cells in poor-outcome childhood precursor-B acute lymphoblastic leukemias. *Leukemia*. 2010 Nov;24(11):1859-66. doi: 10.1038/leu.2010.184. PubMed PMID: 20739953; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC3035974. eng.
13. Vick B, Rothenberg M, Sandhofer N, et al. An advanced preclinical mouse model for acute myeloid leukemia using patients' cells of various genetic subgroups and in vivo bioluminescence imaging. *PloS one*. 2015;10(3):e0120925. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0120925. PubMed PMID: 25793878; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC368518. eng.
14. Terziyska N, Castro Alves C, Groiss V, et al. In vivo imaging enables high resolution preclinical trials on patients' leukemia cells growing in mice. *PloS one*. 2012;7(12):e52798. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0052798. PubMed PMID: 23300782; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC3534096. eng.
15. Walrath JC, Hawes JJ, Van Dyke T, et al. Genetically engineered mouse models in cancer research. *Advances in cancer research*. 2010;106:113-64. doi: 10.1016/s0065-230x(10)06004-5. PubMed PMID: 20399958; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC3533445. eng.

Figure 1: Primary adult ALL samples engraft reliably in NSG mice and allow lentiviral transduction

- A, B** Time required for the first passage of individual PDX ALL samples is shown individually (**A**, numbers indicated unique patient numbers, UPN) or in cumulative form (**B**); samples after a freezing/thawing cycle are indicated with stripes or crosses.
- C** Passaging time of individual samples with BCR-ABL rearrangement over several passages. Statistically significant reduction of passaging time in sample ALL-210 from 165.5 days in P0 to 42 days in P5 according to two-tailed unpaired t-test. P, passage.
- D** Cell viability after 5 days in culture of MLL-rearranged samples either freshly isolated from mice (plain) or after freezing/thawing (stripes). n.r., non-rearranged.
- E, F** PDX samples were lentivirally transduced, kept for 5 days in culture and measured for successful lentiviral transduction by flow cytometry on the recombinant fluorochrome. n.r., non-rearranged.

Handling of fresh primary ALL samples

Fresh primary samples arrived at our research facility typically as unmanipulated heparinized bone marrow suspension within 6 hours after bone marrow aspiration. Leukemia cells were enriched by Ficoll gradient centrifugation and washed twice in PBS containing 1 % fetal calf serum. Cells were frozen in 90% fetal calf serum with 10% DMSO in an isopropanol containing carrier allowing slow temperature decrease [10].

The presence of chromosomal rearrangements was confirmed by both FISH and PCR analysis in most primary samples.

Cell transplantation and analysis of mice to determine engraftment

From 15 adult ALL patient samples, 10^6 to 10^7 primary tumor cells per sample were transplanted into 2-4 NOD/scid gamma (NSG) mice of 6-12 weeks of age by tail vein injection. Engraftment was determined by staining of human CD45, CD38, CD19 (Biolegends, 302205) and CD7 (Life Technologies, MHCD0705) in blood, bone marrow and spleen isolates as measured by flow cytometry [14]. Bone marrow and spleen typically contained >90% human cells at time of sacrifice. After successful engraftment of primary samples, patient derived xenograft (PDX) cells were retransplanted into next generation recipients for up to 4 passages.

Flow cytometry analysis

PDX ALL and AML cells were genetically engineered using lentiviruses as described [13, 14] to express fluorochromes. 10×10^6 cells were infected with concentrated lentivirus overnight in the presence of Polybrene (8 μ g/ml; Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) in RPMI-1640 medium containing 20% fetal calf serum (FCS), 1% penicillin/streptomycin, 1% gentamycin and 2 mM glutamine. The following day, PDX cells were washed and cultivated 5 days *in vitro* in the same medium supplemented with 0.6% Insulin-Transferrin-Selenium (ITS), 1%

sodium-pyruvate and 0.0434% α -Thioglycerol for ALL cells. Cell viability was analyzed by flow cytometry using forward and sideward scatter (FSC-SSC). Positive transduction rate was measured by flow cytometry.

Statistics

All statistical analyses were calculated with a two-tailed unpaired t-test using GraphPad Prism 6 software.

Figure 1

Supplementary Methods:

Ethical statements

Written informed consent was obtained from all patients and from parents/carers in the cases where the patients were minors. The study was performed in accordance with the ethical standards of the responsible committee on human experimentation (written approval by Ethikkommission des Klinikums der Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München, Ethikkommission@med.unimuenchen.de, April 2008, number 068-08 and October 2010, number 222-10) and with the Helsinki Declaration of 1975, as revised in 2000.

All animal trials were performed in accordance with the current ethical standards of the official committee on animal experimentation (written approval by Regierung von Oberbayern, poststelle@reg-ob.bayern.de, September 2010, number 55.2-1-54-2531-95-10, October 2012, number 55.2-1-54-2531.6-10-10 and August 2016, number 55.2-1-54-2532.0-56-2016).

Primary sample sources

Fresh bone marrow (BM) or peripheral blood (PB) aspirates from adult patients with acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) were obtained from the Department of Medicine III, University Hospital, LMU Munich, Germany or Department of Medicine III – Hematology, Oncology and Palliative Care, Rostock University Medical Center, Rostock, Germany.

Acute myeloid leukemia (AML) aspirates were obtained from the Department of Medicine III, University Hospital, LMU Munich, Germany.

Pediatric ALL samples were obtained from the ALL-BFM study group in Kiel, from the Dr. von Haunersches Kinderspital, Ludwig-Maximilian Universität, Munich, Germany.

Figure S1: Overall engraftment and time required for passage 0 of primary adult ALL samples

Means of the data shown in printed Figure 1A or B.

Figure S2: Generation of GEPDX cells *in vivo* in mice

GEPDX cells were generated by repetitive passaging of PDX cells in immunodeficient NSG mice. First, primary cells of acute leukemia patients were engrafted in mice. After reisolation from bone marrow and spleen, cells were genetically engineered using lentiviruses. After another passage in mice, positively transduced cells were enriched by fluorescent-activated cell sorting. AL, acute leukemia; PDX, patient derived xenograft; GEPDX, genetically engineered PDX.

Figure S3: Lentiviral transduction allows bioluminescent *in vivo* imaging of GEPDX cells

After lentiviral transduction of PDX cells, expression of a luciferase, e.g., Gaussia Luciferase, enables leukemia growth monitoring *in vivo* over time. PDX, patient derived xenograft; GEPDX, genetically engineered PDX.

Figure S4: Cell viability after 5 days *in vitro* in culture.

Cell viability was analyzed using forward scatter against side scatter (FSC/SSC). Analysis shown representatively for two samples, PDX ALL-707 and PDX ALL-763 comparing

frozen/thawed and freshly isolated samples after 5 days *in vitro* in culture. PDX, patient derived xenograft; ALL, acute lymphoblastic leukemia.

Figure S5: Lentiviral transduction of acute leukemia PDX cells

A Schematic representation of the lentiviral construct used for PDX cells transduction.

B, C Gating strategy to enrich genetically engineered PDX (GEPDX) cells shown representatively for PDX ALL-223 and AML-393. (**B**: dot plot and **C**: histogram) Cells were always pre-gated on living cells using forward scatter against side scatter (FCS/SSC) (data not shown). EF1 α , Elongation factor 1 alpha; Gluc, Gaussia Luciferase; mtagBFP, monomeric tag blue fluorescent; PDX, patient derived xenograft; GEPDX, genetically engineered PDX.

Table S1: Patients' clinical data and sample characteristics

BM, bone marrow; PB, peripheral blood; UPN, unique patient number; f, female; m, male; n.d., not determined.

Table S2: Engraftment of primary adult rearranged ALL samples

Engraftment data of all samples; raw data to Figures 1A, 1B and S1.

Table S3: Sample source from BM or PB and time required for P0

BM, bone marrow; PB, peripheral blood; P0, passage 0.

Figure S1

Figure S1: Overall engraftment and time required for passage 0 of primary adult ALL samples

Means of the data shown in printed Figure 1A or B.

Figure S2

Figure S2: Generation of GEPDX cells *in vivo* in mice

GEPDX cells were generated by repetitive passaging of PDX cells in immunodeficient NSG mice. First, primary cells from acute leukemia patients were engrafted in mice. After reisolation from bone marrow and spleen, cells were genetically engineered using lentiviruses. After another passage in mice, positively transduced cells were enriched by fluorescent-activated cell sorting. AL, acute leukemia; PDX, patient derived xenograft; GEPDX, genetically engineered PDX.

Figure S3

Figure S3: Lentiviral transduction allows bioluminescent *in vivo* imaging of GEPDX cells
After lentiviral transduction of PDX cells, expression of a luciferase, e.g., Gaussia Luciferase, enables leukemia growth monitoring *in vivo* over time. PDX, patient derived xenograft; GEPDX, genetically engineered PDX.

Figure S4

thawed PDX cells after 5 days *in vitro*

freshly isolated PDX cells after 5 days *in vitro*

Figure S4: Cell viability after 5 days *in vitro* in culture.

Cell viability was analyzed using forward scatter against side scatter (FSC/SSC). Analysis shown representatively for two samples, PDX ALL-707 and PDX ALL-763 comparing thawed and freshly isolated samples after 5 days *in vitro* in culture. PDX, patient derived xenograft; ALL, acute lymphoblastic leukemia.

Figure S5

A

B

C

Figure S5: Lentiviral transduction of acute leukemia PDX cells

A: Schematic representation of the lentiviral construct used for PDX cells transduction. **B and C:** Gating strategy to enrich GEPDX cells shown representatively for PDX ALL-223 and AML-393. (**B:** dot plot and **C:** histogram) Cells were always pre-gated on living cells using forward scatter against side scatter (FCS/SSC) (data not shown). EF1 α , Elongation factor 1 alpha; Gluc, Gaussia Luciferase; mtagBFP, monomeric tag blue fluorescent; PDX, patient derived xenograft; GEPDX, genetically engineered PDX.

Table S1

Table S1: Patients' clinical data and sample characteristics

UPN	subtype	Age (years)	Gender	Disease status	Sample type	Cytogenetic	Major cytogenetic group
ALL-352	adult	67	m	Diagnosis	PB	46,XY,t(4;11)(q21;q23)[2]/46,XY[23]	t(4;11)
ALL-389	adult	43	f	Diagnosis	BM	45,XX,t(4;11)(q21;q23),i(7)(q10),del(9)(p1?3),dic(12;17)(p1?2;p1?2)[8]/ 44,XX,sl,der(X)t(X;9)(q2?;?),-9[3]/	t(4;11)
ALL-816	adult	52	f	Diagnosis	PB	46,XX,t(4;11)(q21;q23)	t(4;11)
ALL-817	adult	74	f	Diagnosis	PB	46,XX,t(4;11)(q21;q23)[19]/46,XX[6]FISH: MLL+	t(4;11)
ALL-818	adult	47	m	Diagnosis	PB	46,XY,t(4;11)(q21;q23)[13]/47,XY,+X,t(4;11)(q21;q23),-9,+21[1]/48,XY,+X,t(4;11)(q21;q23),+21[2]/46,XY[1]	t(4;11)
AML-388	adult	57	m	Diagnosis	BM	t(6;11); FLT3 -, NPM1 -, CEBPA - t(9;11); CEBPA ?, karyotype 46,XX,t(9;11)(p22;q23)[20]/46,XX[3]; myeloma, pancytopenia; FLT3 -, NPM1 -, FISH: MLL [74/114]	t(6;11)
AML-669	adult	49	f	Relapse	PB	MLL [74/114]	t(9;11)
AML-393	adult	47	f	Relapse	BM	t(10;11); CEBPA n.a., karyotype aberrant; FLT3 -, NPM1 -	t(10;11)
ALL-209	adult	61	f	Relapse	BM	45,XX,t(2;7)(p1?;p1?),del(3)(p12),-9,t(9;22)(q34;q11),del(15)(q1?) [7]/46,XX[6] 48,XX,+X,der(2)t(2;7)(p?;p?),+5,- 7,der(9)t(9;13)(?;q11)t(2;9)(?;?),t(9;22)(q34;q11),der(13)t(9;13)(?;q11),+der(22)t(9;22)(q34;q11)[9]	t(9;22)
ALL-210	adult	35	f	Diagnosis	BM	7,der(9)t(9;13)(?;q11)t(2;9)(?;?),t(9;22)(q34;q11),der(13)t(9;13)(?;q11),+der(22)t(9;22)(q34;q11)[9]	t(9;22)
ALL-223	adult	48	f	Diagnosis	PB	n.d., FISH t(9;22)	t(9;22)
ALL-224	adult	70	f	Diagnosis	PB	46,XX,del(5)(q?31),del(5*)(q?31),del(7)(p12),t(9;22)(q34;q11),del(11)(q1?3) [9]	t(9;22)
ALL-256	adult	41	f	Diagnosis	PB	47,XX,+8,t(9;22)(q34;q11),der(9)t(9;22)(q34;q11), ish (ABL1x3),(BCRx4),(ABL1 con BCRx3)	t(9;22)
ALL-262	adult	42	m	Diagnosis	BM	48,XY,+der(5)t(5;?22),-22,+der(22)t(9;22)(q34;q11.2)x2[2]/46,XY[18]	t(9;22)
ALL-360	adult	33	f	Diagnosis	BM	n.d., FISH t(9;22), del(9), del(17)	t(9;22)
ALL-363	adult	66	m	Diagnosis	PB	46,XY,t(9;22)(q34;q11)[2]/46,XY[5]	t(9;22)
ALL-589	adult	44	m	Diagnosis	BM	46,XY,t(9;22)(q34;q11.2),+21,der(22)t(9;22)(q34;q11.2)[6]/ 46,XY,t(9;22)(q34;q11.2)[21]	t(9;22)
ALL-590	adult	84	m	Diagnosis	PB	46,XY[13] FISH: bcr/abl positiv, del(9)(p21) (=p16)	t(9;22)
ALL-199	pediatric	8	f	Relapse	BM	trisomy 21; no detection of the following fusion transcripts: E2A-PBX1, MLL-AF4, MLL-ENL, p190 BCR-ABL, p210 BCR-ABL, TEL-AML147,XX,+21c. . . nuc ish 6q23 (MYBx2) /oo7, 9,P2- (P16x0), cen9 (C&P9x2) [19/100(, 9q34 (ABLx2), 22q11 (BcRx1) I).oo], 1	trisomy 21
ALL-265	pediatric	5	f	Relapse	BM	trisomy 21	trisomy 21
AML-346	pediatric	1	f	Relapse	unknown	interstitial 5q deletion and interstitial 13q deletion.; FLT3 -, NPM1 -, MLL -, CEBPA -,	normal
ALL-706	pediatric	5	f	Diagnosis	BM	46,XX,t(4;11)(q21;q23)[11]/46,XX[3] 46,XY,t(4;11)(q21;q23),del(17)(p12)[1]/46,XY[24] nuc ish 11q23(MLLx2),17p13,1(P53x2)[100]	t(4;11)
ALL-707	pediatric	2	m	Diagnosis	PB	46,XY,t(4;11)(q21;q23)[13]/46, idem,del(17)(p12)[5]/46,XY[3] nuc ish 11q23(MLLx2)(5'MLLsep3'MLLx1)[80/100],12p13(TELx2),21q22(AML1x2)[100]17p13.1(P53x1)[20/100]	t(4;11)
ALL-762	pediatric	1	f	Diagnosis	PB	46,XX,t(4;11)(q21;q23),inc[11]/46,XX[1] 46,XX[12], nuc ish 4q21-22(AFF1x2),11q23(MLLx2)[100] 46,XX,t(2;4;11)(p22;q21;q23)7add(6)(q24)[17]/46,XX[3], nuc ish 4q21-	t(4;11)
ALL-763	pediatric	17	f	Diagnosis	BM	22(AF4x3),11q23(MLLx3)(AF4conMLL2x2)[78/100]6q23(MYBx2),9q34(ABLx2),22q11(BCRx2),14q32(IGHx2), nuc ish 12q13(TELx2),21q22(AML1x2)[100],9p21(P16x1),cen9(CEP9x2)[52/100],11q23(MLLx2)(5'MLLsep3'MLLx1)[92/100]	t(4;11)
ALL-703	pediatric	1	f	Diagnosis	BM	46,XX,t(9;11)(p22;q23)[7]/46,XX[7] nuc ish 9q34(ABLx2),22q11(BCRx2)(100),12p13(TELx2),21q22(AML1x2)(100) 46,XX,t(9;11)(p22;q23)[6]/46,XX[7] nuc ish	t(9;11)
ALL-704	pediatric	1	f	Diagnosis	BM	9q34(ABLx2),22q11(BCRx2)[100],11q23(5'MLL,3'MLLx2)(5'MLLsep3'MLLx1)[77/100],12p13(TELx2),21q22(AML1x2)[100]	t(9;11)
ALL-705	pediatric	1	f	Diagnosis	BM	n.d. t(9;11)	t(9;11)

BM, bone marrow; PB, peripheral blood; UPN, unique patient number; f, female; m, male; n.d., not determined.

Table S2

	number of engrafting samples	in %
all	13\15	86.68
fresh only	5\5	100
frozen only	8\10	80
t(9;22) all	8\10	80
t(9;22) fresh only	3\3	100
t(9;22) frozen only	5\7	71.43
t(4;11) all	5\5	100
t(4;11) fresh only	2\2	100
t(4;11) frozen only	3\3	100